

NOTES

Synthesis, Spectral and Magnetic Studies of Nickel(II) Complexes with Schiff Bases of Heterocyclic Aldehyde

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Manuscript received 17 March 1986, revised 21 September 1987, accepted 30 October 1987

IN continuation of the previous work^{1,2} the synthesis of some Ni^{II} complexes with biological active Schiff bases derived from 2-acetylfuran or 2-furylglyoxal with *o*-aminobenzoic acid, ethylenediamine, aniline-*o*-sulphonic acid, 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline and some of their spectral and magnetic properties and fungicidal activity are described.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. 2-Acetylfuran and glyoxal were prepared according to literature method^{3,4}. All the ligands were prepared by the method reported earlier⁵.

Preparation of complexes: A solution of the metal salt (10 mmol) and ligand (10 mmol) (1 : 1) was refluxed in ethanol (100 ml) on a water-bath for 2–3 h. On cooling the contents a coloured precipitate was obtained, washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are soluble in common organic solvents, while insoluble in coordinating solvent, viz. DMF, DMA and DMSO *etc.* The magnetic moment values (3.20–2.98 B.M.) of the complexes at 300 K correspond to their octahedral geometry^{7,8}. A slight higher value than the spin-only moment (2.83 B.M.) arises probably due to slight distortion from *O_h* to *D_{4h}* symmetry.

The electronic spectra of the complexes showed three different bands at ~ 8 000–9 000, 14 000–15 000 and 24 000–25 000 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) (ν_2) and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) transitions, respectively, indicating an octahedral configuration for the Ni^{II} complexes, which is further confirmed by ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.6–1.8)⁹. With the help of Konig equations¹⁰, various electronic parameters such as B_{22} , β_{22} , λ , ν_3/ν_1 , $10 Dq$ and B have been calculated which are in close agreement with the structure of Ni^{II} octahedral geometry, somewhat distorted.

The IR spectra of the four Schiff bases exhibit two bands at ~ 1 620 (C=N) and ~ 1 690 cm⁻¹ (C=O). These bands show lower shift in the spectra of the corresponding metal complexes indicating the involvement of nitrogen of C=N group¹¹ and oxygen of C=O group¹² on complexation. In the case of ligands, 2-FMCKA and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY DATA OF Ni^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd	Decomp. temp. °C	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Inhibition %* against		
			Ni	N	Cl	S	<i>H. gramineum</i>	<i>S. racamosus</i>	<i>O. capsici</i>
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₂) ₂]2H ₂ O	260	Ash green	10.25 (10.69)	4.95 (4.10)	—	—	44.32 (52.32)	57.64 (69.08)	50.04 (52.34)
[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂)(NO ₂) ₂]2H ₂ O	218	Cream	11.40 (11.96)	11.20 (11.41)	—	—	80.00 (87.46)	67.45 (79.34)	68.45 (76.78)
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSO ₂) ₂]2H ₂ O	240	Brownish black	8.91 (9.02)	4.09 (4.30)	—	9.60 (9.83)	55.35 (65.34)	65.04 (92.40)	59.63 (87.44)
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl) ₂](NO ₂) ₂	180	Yellow	7.50 (7.98)	11.12 (11.85)	9.28 (9.59)	—	48.07 (56.92)	68.33 (78.45)	64.28 (78.34)

*Average % of inhibition after 5 days of radial growth at 100 ppm, Temp. = 28 ± 2°.

Nickel, nitrogen, sulphur and halogen in the complexes were estimated (Table 1) by standard methods⁶. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in solid state were recorded on a Pye-Unicam-SP-500 spectrophotometer.

2-CNA2FG, a sharp band observed at ~ 1 290 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{C-O-C} of furyl ring¹³. In the IR spectra of the complexes, there is a considerable lowering of this frequency suggesting coordination through the oxygen of the furyl ring also. In the complexes of 2-FMCKA and 2-FGSAA, the complete

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disappearance of the broad band at ~ 2620 and $\sim 1140\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, indicates the deprotonation of carboxylic hydrogen and sulphonic acid hydrogen and its participation in coordination¹⁴. The presence of water of crystallisation is indicated in the spectra of Ni^{II} complexes of 2-FMCKA, 2-FGED and 2-FGSAA because there is a peak at $3190\text{--}3290\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The new bands observed in the complexes at ~ 470 and $\sim 410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, respectively¹⁵. The ir spectra of Ni^{II} complex of 2-FGED show the presence of bidentate chelating nitrate group¹⁶.

Screening of fungicidal activity: The antifungal activity of the compounds was checked by food-poison technique. Seven days old culture of *Helminthosporium gramineum* (causing stripe disease in barley), *Syncephalostrum racemosus* (causing fruit rot of tomato) and *Colleotrichium capsici* (causing die back disease in chillies) were used as test organism which were grown on potato dextrose-agar medium. The fungi were grown at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ and the average of three replications was recorded. The percentage inhibition¹⁷ was calculated as $100 \times (C - T)/C$ where, C = diameter of fungus colony in control plate and T = diameter of fungus colony in test plate. All the complexes and ligands were found to be highly active against all the fungi tested (Table 1). The metal complexes were more active in all the cases than their ligands, which is in accordance with the previous established fact that chelation of metal to ligand increases the fungitoxicity of the molecule¹⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. R. C. Sexena, Chemistry Department, M. M. College, Modinagar, for helpful discussions. One of the authors (R.D.) is also thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for a Senior Research Fellowship.

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X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) Tungstate

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Manuscript received 24 September 1986, revised 3 August 1987, accepted 7 September 1987

IN continuation to our investigation¹ on Ni^{II} complexes with unsaturated amines as ligands we here-in report the powder X-ray diffraction data for the complex tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) tungstate.

Experimental

The experimental details, elemental analyses, magnetic, visible and ir spectral data have already been reported in earlier communication¹. The X-ray data were recorded at the University of Aberdeen, Scotland, U.K. on a Phillips X-ray machine attached with a diffractogram. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ at $5\text{--}60^\circ (2\theta)$ using the scale, $1^\circ = 1\text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the title compound suggest the molecular formula as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_3\text{WO}_4$.

The diffractogram has been shown in Fig. 1 which records in all 18 reflections between 5 and $60^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta = 10.1^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 8.7576\text{ \AA}$. The 2θ values for prominent peaks have been listed in Table 1. All main peaks have been indexed and their $\sin^2\theta$ values compared with the calculated ones. Comparison of the values reveal that there is a good agreement between calculated and observed values of $\sin^2\theta$. The unit cell has been calculated by the trial and error method²⁻⁴. The observed values fit well in the tetragonal system to give a unit cell with lattice constants, $a = 12.3853\text{ \AA}$, $C = 12.9269\text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $1982.930\text{ \AA}^3$. Substitution of this cell volume primitive lattice ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 1.7711 g cm^{-3} . The experimental